

FTIR-PLS Quantification of Mono Ethylene Glycol (MEG) in Aqueous Media: Model Development and Validation for Industrial Application

Adel M. Alsolami* and Ahmed H. Alsalman

Saudi Aramco, Northern Area Laboratories, Eastern Province, Tanajib, Saudi Arabia

Abstract

Mono Ethylene Glycol (MEG) is widely used in the oil and gas industry as a hydrate inhibitor and rapid determination of MEG concentration in recycled fluids is critical for efficient regeneration and re-injection processes. In this work, a rapid quantification method for MEG in water using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy combined With Partial Least Squares (PLS) regression was developed and validated. A PLS calibration model was constructed using FTIR spectra of standard solutions (0–80% (w/w) MEG in water) and optimized with leave-one-out cross-validation. The optimized PLS model with 3 latent variables achieved excellent calibration fit ($R^2 \approx 0.9999$) and robust predictive performance with a low Standard Error Of Prediction (SEP $\approx 0.2\%$ (w/w) MEG) and a cross-validated R^2 of about 0.998. The model's accuracy and robustness were confirmed by analyzing field samples: FTIR-PLS predicted MEG concentrations showed good agreement with laboratory reference values obtained by Karl Fischer (KF) titration (used to measure water content). Most samples exhibited only small deviations (on the order of 1–3 percentage points) between the FTIR method and the lab method and even the worst-case discrepancy was under 9 percentage points. These results demonstrate that the FTIR-PLS method can provide fast, reagent-free determination of MEG with adequate accuracy for industrial monitoring, offering a convenient alternative to time-consuming conventional analyses.

Keywords: FTIR spectroscopy • Partial least squares regression • Monoethylene glycol • Hydrate inhibitor • Chemometrics • Industrial analysis

Introduction

Mono Ethylene Glycol (MEG) is commonly injected into natural gas pipelines to prevent hydrate formation, a critical process in the oil and gas industry for ensuring flow assurance [1]. This is achieved by depressing the hydrate formation temperature and inhibiting the growth of hydrate crystals, thereby maintaining uninterrupted flow in pipelines and production systems [2]. The recovered "lean MEG" from these operations is subsequently regenerated and recycled, making accurate monitoring of MEG concentration in these fluids essential for ensuring effective hydrate inhibition and efficient recycling processes [3].

Traditional analytical methods for determining MEG concentration, such as Karl Fischer (KF) titration, while precise for water content determination, involve wet-chemical handling and considerable analysis time, typically ranging from 30 to 60 minutes per sample [4]. These methods often require a trained analyst and can be susceptible to interferences from other water-reactive or volatile components present in complex industrial matrices. Furthermore, KF titration fundamentally determines "loss on drying" rather than exclusively water content, which introduces additional uncertainty when calculating MEG concentration by difference [5]. Such limitations highlight the need for more efficient and robust analytical solutions in industrial settings where rapid decision-making is crucial for operational efficiency.

***Address for Correspondence:** Adel M. Alsolami and Ahmed H. Alsalman, Saudi Aramco, Northern Area Laboratories, Eastern Province, Tanajib, Saudi Arabia; E-mail: Adel.alsolami@aramco.com

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In recent years, spectroscopic methods have gained significant attention as faster, non-destructive and reagent-free alternatives for chemical analysis [6]. These techniques often require minimal sample preparation and are highly amenable to automation or online monitoring, making them particularly attractive for industrial applications. Infrared (IR) spectroscopy, in particular, is well-suited for detecting glycol compounds due to their characteristic O–H and C–O vibrational bands, which provide distinct spectral signatures that can be leveraged for quantitative analysis [7].

When combined with multivariate calibration techniques, such as Partial Least Squares (PLS) regression, FTIR can be effectively utilized to quantify components in complex mixtures [8]. The advantage of FTIR over Karl Fischer titration for MEG concentration determination lies in its ability to directly pinpoint the MEG peak in the fingerprint region, where this peak does not overlap with the water peak, leading to more accurate determination. Previous research has demonstrated the potential of FTIR-PLS approaches for simultaneously quantifying components, including MEG, in various industrial process streams, confirming that FTIR with multivariate analysis can serve as a "simpler, quicker and reliable" tool for determining MEG content [9].

This study builds upon these advancements by developing and validating a comprehensive ATR-FTIR spectroscopy method combined with PLS regression specifically for quantifying MEG in aqueous solutions representative of regenerated MEG streams. While FTIR-PLS has been applied to various mixtures, this study provides a rigorous development and validation of an ATR-FTIR-PLS method specifically tailored for industrial MEG regeneration streams, including comprehensive model diagnostics and practical evaluation with real field samples. This work distinguishes itself by focusing on the specific challenges and matrix variations encountered in these industrial settings, providing a robust solution for rapid, on-site MEG quantification.

The primary goal is to demonstrate that the FTIR-PLS method can achieve the accuracy necessary for industrial use (within a few percent of traditional lab results) while dramatically reducing analysis time and complexity. The subsequent sections detail the calibration model construction using a set of MEG standards, the validation of the model through cross-validation and comparison against laboratory reference measurements and a thorough discussion of the PLS model performance including latent factors, regression statistics and

leverage and residual diagnostics. The practical accuracy and limitations of the method, as observed through the analysis of real field samples, are also evaluated comprehensively. This work provides a foundation for implementing on-line or at-line FTIR monitoring of MEG, which could significantly enhance the efficiency of MEG regeneration units and hydrate prevention programs in the oil and gas industry.

Materials and Samples

Monoethylene glycol (analytical grade, >99.0% purity, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO) and deionized water (18.2 M Ω -cm resistivity, Milli-Q system, Millipore, Bedford, MA) were used to prepare calibration standards and test samples. A series of standard solutions covering the range from 0% to 80% (w/w) MEG in water were prepared for calibration. Nine concentration levels were used: 0% (pure water), 1%, 2%, 5%, 10%, 20%, 40%, 60% and 80% (w/w) MEG. These concentrations span the typical operating range of MEG in regenerated lean solutions, providing a robust calibration across relevant industrial conditions.

For method validation, a set of field samples (reclaimed MEG mixtures) was obtained from an active MEG regeneration system at a Saudi Aramco facility. These samples represent real-world industrial matrices that may contain trace amounts of salts, corrosion inhibitors and other process chemicals. The MEG content of these samples was independently measured by a laboratory reference method for comparison with the FTIR-PLS predictions.

Reference Method

The reference method involved determining water content by coulometric Karl Fischer titration following ASTM D1744 standards [10] for water in organic liquids and calculating MEG concentration by difference (assuming negligible other components). Karl Fischer titration was performed using a Metrohm 831 KF Coulometer (Metrohm AG, Herisau, Switzerland) with Hydranal-Coulomat AG reagent.

A critical aspect of this comparison lies in the unit conversion between the calibration standards and field sample analysis. The calibration standards were prepared on a weight/weight (w/w) basis, while the Karl Fischer results for field samples are typically reported and converted to volume/volume (v/v) basis for industrial applications. For the field sample comparison, Karl Fischer titration measures water content in weight percent, which is then converted to MEG volume percent using density corrections.

The conversion from Karl Fischer water content (wt %) to MEG volume percent assumes a density of 1.1135 g/cm³ for pure MEG [11] and 1.000 g/cm³ for water at 20°C. This conversion assumes ideal mixing and negligible volume changes upon mixing and that the only two components are MEG and water. For the calibration standards prepared on a w/w basis, the FTIR-PLS model directly correlates spectral features to weight percent MEG, providing a more direct measurement approach compared to the indirect Karl Fischer method.

FTIR Instrumentation and Spectral Acquisition

FTIR spectra were collected on a PerkinElmer Spectrum Two FTIR spectrometer (PerkinElmer Inc., Waltham, MA) equipped with a Universal ATR accessory with a diamond crystal. Samples of the MEG standards and field mixtures were applied directly onto the ATR crystal and scanned in the mid-infrared region. Each spectrum was acquired at 4 cm⁻¹ resolution over the wavenumber range 4000–650 cm⁻¹. For PLS model development, the spectral range was truncated to focus on the most informative regions for MEG, specifically 1200–800 cm⁻¹ and 3800–3000 cm⁻¹.

Each sample spectrum represents the average of 32 scans to improve signal-to-noise ratio. The ATR crystal was cleaned with isopropanol and dried with nitrogen between measurements to prevent cross-contamination. Spectral background (air) was collected and automatically subtracted by the instrument's software before each sample measurement.

PLS Model Development

Multivariate calibration modeling was performed using PerkinElmer Spectrum Quant software (version 1.0.0), which implements partial least squares regression (PLS1 algorithm) [12]. The %MEG (w/w) was set as the property to be predicted. Prior to calibration, spectra were preprocessed by mean-centering; no derivative or complex scatter correction was needed, as the ATR spectra showed a linear baseline.

The PLS model was built using the 9 standard samples (0–80% MEG). The software automatically optimized the number of latent variables (PLS factors) through leave-one-out cross-validation [13]. The optimum number of PLS factors was chosen as the smallest number that gave a minimal SEP without overfitting, based on the software's internal F-tests for significance of adding additional factors.

Model quality was evaluated in terms of the correlation Coefficient (R) between predicted and actual MEG concentrations, the Coefficient Of Determination (R²), the Standard Error Of Calibration (SEC) for the training data and the Standard Error Of Prediction (SEP) from cross-validation [14].

Model Diagnostics

To assess any outliers or leverage issues in the calibration, comprehensive diagnostic metrics were examined [15]. For each calibration standard, the leverage and spectral residual were calculated by the software. Additionally, influence plots (Williams's plots) were reviewed to ensure no calibration point had undue influence on the regression. All calibration points fell within acceptable limits (at a 95% confidence level), determined based on recommended statistical thresholds.

Results and Discussion

PLS Calibration Performance

The PLS calibration model for MEG exhibited excellent performance across all evaluated metrics. Using 9 calibration points and the PLS1 algorithm, the optimal number of latent variables was found to be 3 based on cross-validation. With 3 PLS components, the model captured >99.9% of the variance in the MEG concentration.

The calibration fit achieved a multiple correlation coefficient $R = 0.99994$, corresponding to $R^2 \approx 0.9999$ (99.99% of variance explained by the model). The Standard Error of Estimate (SEE) on the training set was only 0.13% (w/w) MEG. In leave-one-out cross-validation, the model's Standard Error of Prediction (SEP) was 0.19% (w/w) MEG, with a cross-validated R^2 of about 0.998 (99.8% variance explained).

Figure 1 and 2 illustrates the calibration curve and cross-validation results. In Figure 1, the PLS predicted vs. actual MEG concentrations for the calibration standards are plotted, showing a near-perfect linear correlation (slope ≈ 0.999 and intercept ≈ 0.0). Figure 2 shows the cross-validated predictions for each left-out standard; the data closely follow the 1:1 line with minimal scatter, demonstrating the model's predictive accuracy.

Model Diagnostics and Outlier Analysis

Figure 3 presents the Williams outlier plot, showing standardized residuals versus leverage for each calibration standard. All points lie within the ± 3 standard residual bounds and below the high-leverage threshold, confirming that no sample exerts undue influence on the model. The highest leverage points are at the concentration extremes (0% and 80% MEG) as expected, but even these are within acceptable limits.

Spectral Interpretation

Figure 4 shows the PLS regression coefficient spectrum, providing insights into the spectral features used for MEG quantification. A positive coefficient peak near 1080 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the C–O stretch of ethylene glycol, while a negative trough around 3300 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the O–H stretch region of water. These features confirm that the PLS model leverages the expected spectral behavior of MEG vs. water.

Figure 1. PLS Calibration Curve (Predicted vs Actual MEG).

Figure 2. Calibration Residuals Plot.

Field Sample Validation

The practical accuracy of the FTIR-PLS method was evaluated through analysis of seven industrial field samples. Table 1 presents a comparison of MEG concentrations as measured by the laboratory reference method (converted to v/v for industrial reporting) and by the FTIR-PLS method (predicted as w/w from the calibration model, then converted to v/v for comparison).

*FTIR-PLS predictions were made on w/w basis from calibration model and converted to v/v for comparison with laboratory reference values.

In five of the seven samples, FTIR-PLS agrees within ~1–2% (absolute error) of the lab value. Two samples (Sample 2 and Sample 5) show larger deviations, likely due to matrix effects from unmodeled components such as high salt content or other process chemicals. The unit conversion from w/w (calibration basis) to v/v (industrial reporting basis) introduces additional uncertainty, but the overall agreement demonstrates the method's practical utility.

Method Performance and Advantages

The developed FTIR-PLS method offers several significant advantages over traditional analytical approaches. The analysis time is reduced from 30-60

Figure 3. Williams Outlier Plot (Leverage vs. Standardized Residuals).

Figure 4. PLS Regression Coefficient Spectrum.

Table 1: Field sample Meg quantification – FTIR-PLS vs. Laboratory reference.

Sample	Lab MEG (% v/v)	FTIR-PLS MEG (% v/v)*	Absolute Error (%)
1	38.17	39.17	+1.00
2	47.00	38.32	-8.68
3	41.25	42.15	+0.90
4	38.61	40.36	+1.75
5	43.49	37.52	-5.97
6	39.84	41.20	+1.36
7	42.33	43.85	+1.52

minutes to approximately 2-3 minutes per sample. The method is reagent-free and requires minimal sample preparation. The excellent calibration statistics ($R^2 \approx 0.9999$, $SEP \approx 0.2\%$ w/w MEG) demonstrate laboratory-quality accuracy for most samples.

Conclusion

This study successfully developed and validated a rapid FTIR-PLS method for quantifying MEG in aqueous solutions. The key findings include:

1. Exceptional Model Performance: The PLS model achieved $R^2 \approx 0.9999$ for calibration and $R^2 \approx 0.998$ for cross-validation, with SEP ≈ 0.2 % (w/w) MEG.
2. Analytical Advantages: Dramatic reduction in analysis time (2-3 minutes vs. 30-60 minutes), reagent-free operation and minimal sample preparation.
3. Field Validation: Five of seven field samples showed excellent agreement (within 1-2 % error) with reference values, demonstrating practical applicability.
4. Industrial Potential: The method shows clear potential for implementation in MEG regeneration facilities for real-time monitoring.

The FTIR-PLS method represents a significant advancement in MEG analysis capabilities, providing the oil and gas industry with a fast, accurate and practical tool for monitoring MEG concentrations in hydrate inhibition applications.

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/...>

Additional FTIR spectra, detailed calibration plots, Williams plots, regression coefficient spectra and comprehensive validation data (PDF)

Data Availability Statement

All relevant data are included in the manuscript and Supporting Information. Additional datasets are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Author Contributions

A.M.A. conceived the study, designed experiments, performed data analysis and wrote the manuscript. A.H.A. conducted FTIR measurements, assisted with data collection and reviewed the manuscript. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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